

Dynamic Eclipse Broadcast (DEB) Initiative

Scripting Installation and Setup

1 July 2025

(DEB Information at debinitiative.org)

Installation:

- 1) Place Base_python_scripts files in the folder you intend to use for Programs.
 - a. Default is **C:\DEB\Programs**, but, with the deb_util.py functionality, you can put these in any folder you wish, as long as you edit deb.ini correctly (described below)
 - b. All scripts (python programs) should be in the “Programs” folder (see below)

- 2) Use python to run 'C:\DEB\Programs\deb_util.py' from a command prompt. . .Examples below that you can try to run from the command line:
 - a. `python C:\DEB\Programs\deb_util.py`
 - b. `C:\Users\YOURUSERNAME\miniconda3\python C:\DEB\Programs\deb_util.py`
- 3) Open C:\Users\YOURUSERNAME\deb.ini in a text editor
 - a. You will see something like the image below

```
deb_dummy - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
[DEFAULT]
python_version = python
search_path = C:\Users
filename = planetary_system_stacker.py
output_format = png
partial_ser_time = 15
partial_interval_sec = 60
down_size = True
down_size_percent = 60
deb_path = C:\DEB
deb_programs = C:\DEB\Programs
debconf_version = 2
siu_upload_host = 131.230.106.9

[SITE]
comment = The "site" field can be used to point to persistent customizations.
site = SITE
site_siu_folder = 001deb
site_siu_ssh_key = DEB1_rsa

[FU_deb_test]
site = FU_53
site_id = 53
site_name = Castor Fu deb test
deb_programs = C:\Users\Casto\src\debi-private
site_siu_folder = 004deb
site_siu_ssh_key = id_deb004

[FU_deb_prod]
site = FU_53
site_id = 53
site_name = Castor Fu deb prod
site_siu_folder = 004deb
site_siu_ssh_key = id_deb004
```

We will concentrate on the [SITE] portion for now (highlighted with red outline)

- b. "site_siu_folder = 001deb" needs to be your folder designation (ex. 002deb, 003deb, etc.)
 - i. **Follow directions in "Instructions-Uploading" file for setting up your folder if you have not already done so**
- c. "site_siu_ssh_key = DEB1_rsa" should match the key name in your .ssh folder that was used to setup your uploading (see below for example of contents of .ssh folder)

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
id_rsa	6/27/2024 11:11 AM	File	3 KB
id_rsa	6/27/2024 11:11 AM	Microsoft Publish...	1 KB
known_hosts	9/1/2023 12:48 PM	File	1 KB

- i. This was covered in "Instructions-Uploading" from above, so you should have already created this file when you setup uploading.
- d. You will add a "python version" into this section that matches your python installation. This will need to point to your preferred python installation if you have more than one. (see below)

```
[SITE]
comment = The "site" field can be used to point to persistent customizations.
site = SITE
site_siu_folder = 001deb
site_siu_ssh_key = DEB1_rsa
python_version = C:\Users\DEB\miniconda3\python.exe
```

- e. You will add a specific path to the planetary_system_stacker installation folder with the "search_path" variable. (see below)

```
[SITE]
comment = The "site" field can be used to point to persistent customizations.
site = SITE
site_siu_folder = 001deb
site_siu_ssh_key = DEB1_rsa
python_version = C:\Users\DEB\miniconda3\python.exe
search_path = C:\Users\DEB\miniconda3\Lib\site-packages\planetary_system_stacker
```

- f. Save the file after making the edits

End of Document

This material is based upon work supported by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration under Grant No. 80NSSC23K0948 issued through Science Mission Directorate

This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. 2215167